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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

STRATEGIYA VA IJRONI UYG‘UNLASHTIRISH: O‘ZBEKISTON QANDOLAT BOZORI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV YONDASHUVI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezisda O‘zbekiston qandolat sanoati misolida strategiya va ijroni uyg‘unlashtirishning iqtisodiy ahamiyati, raqobatbardoshlikni ta‘minlashdagi o‘rni hamda strategik boshqaruvning amaliy mexanizmlari tahlil qilingan. So‘nggi yillarda qandolat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish hajmi, eksport ulushi va mahalliy brendlarning nufuzi oshib borayotgan bo‘lsa-da, bozorda raqobat kuchaymoqda. Shu sababli korxonalarda strategik boshqaruv madaniyatini shakllantirish, samarali ijro tizimini yaratish va innovatsion yondashuvlarni qo‘llash zarurati yuzaga kelmoqda. Tadqiqotda raqamli marketing, brend menejment va ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish strategiyalari asosiy yo‘nalish sifatida taklif etiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: strategik boshqaruv, raqobatbardoshlik, innovatsion rivojlanish, ijro tizimi, qandolat bozori, eksport salohiyati, strategiya uyg‘unligi.

Kirish

Bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining muvaffaqiyati nafaqat ularning moliyaviy resurslariga, balki to‘g‘ri tanlangan strategik yo‘nalish va samarali ijroga ham bog‘liq. Ayniqsa, qandolat sanoati O‘zbekiston oziq-ovqat tarmog‘ining muhim segmenti sifatida ichki talabni qondirish, yangi ish o‘rinlari yaratish va eksport salohiyatini oshirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Hozirgi kunda mamlakatimizda 270 dan ortiq yirik va o‘rta qandolat ishlab chiqaruvchilari faoliyat yuritmoqda. Ularning aksariyati mahalliy xomashyodan foydalangan holda raqobatbardosh mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarmoqda. Biroq xalqaro bozorda muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun faqat ishlab chiqarish hajmini oshirish emas, balki strategik boshqaruv va ijroni uyg‘unlashtirish tamoyillarini amaliyotga joriy etish zarur.

Strategik boshqaruv — bu korxonaning uzoq muddatli rivojlanish yo‘nalishini belgilash, resurslardan oqilona foydalanish va natijaga yo‘naltirilgan ijro tizimini yaratish jarayonidir. Qandolat sanoati misolida bu yondashuv ishlab chiqaruvchilarga o‘z brendini shakllantirish, bozordagi o‘rni mustahkamlash hamda innovatsion texnologiyalar asosida mahsulot sifatini oshirish imkonini beradi.

Asosiy qism

Strategik boshqaruvning samaradorligi, avvalo, bozorni chuqur tahlil qilish, iste‘molchi ehtiyojini o‘rganish va resurslardan oqilona foydalanishga bog‘liq. Qandolat sanoatida ushbu yondashuv quyidagi asosiy yo‘nalishlarda o‘z ifodasini topadi:

Bozor tahlili va iste'molchi xatti-harakati

O'zbekiston bozorida qandolat mahsulotlariga bo'lgan talab yil sayin oshib bormoqda. Aholining o'rtacha daromadining o'sishi, turizmning rivojlanishi va oziq-ovqat sanoatining modernizatsiyasi iste'mol hajmini kengaytirgan. Biroq import mahsulotlar bilan raqobat hali ham yuqori bo'lib, bu mahalliy ishlab chiqaruvchilardan sifat va narx siyosatini muvozanatli yuritishni talab qiladi.

Strategik boshqaruv va ijroning uyg'unligi

Korxonalar uchun faqat strategiya ishlab chiqish emas, balki uni to'g'ri amalga oshirish mexanizmlarini yaratish ham muhimdir. Bunda:

- **Tashkiliy tuzilmaning** moslashuvchanligi;
- **Raqamli transformatsiya** (ERP, CRM, AI tizimlari orqali ishlab chiqarishni boshqarish);
- **Motivatsion tizimni** joriy etish;
- **Sifat menejmenti va marketing strategiyasini** uyg'unlashtirish zarur.

Innovatsion boshqaruv elementlari

Zamonaviy texnologiyalar (avtomatlashtirilgan qadoqlash, energiya tejavchi pechlar, raqamli tahlil dasturlari) ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarini kamaytiradi, mahsulot sifatini oshiradi va brend imijini mustahkamlaydi. Misol uchun, "Shirin", "Rohat", "Nestle Uzbekistan" kabi korxonalar innovatsion liniyalar orqali eksport ulushini oshirishga erishgan.

1-diagramma. O'zbekiston qandolat sanoati tahlili (2020–2024-yillar)

2020–2024-yillar oralig'ida qandolat sanoatining o'sish sur'atlari barqaror. Eng katta o'sish eksport hajmida kuzatilgan bo'lib, 108 foizni tashkil etgan. Bu raqamlar ichki ishlab chiqarish va brend imijining kuchaygani, strategik boshqaruv mexanizmlarining amalda samarali ishlayotganini ko'rsatadi. Biroq eksport geografiyasining torligi (asosan Qozog'iston, Tojikiston, Qirg'iziston bilan cheklangan) yangi bozorlarni egallash zarurligini ko'rsatadi.

Xulosa

Qandolat sanoatida strategiya va ijroni uyg'unlashtirish quyidagi natijalarga olib keladi:

1. Korxonalar faoliyatida strategik fikrlash va tahliliy yondashuv mustahkamlanadi.
2. Innovatsion va raqamli texnologiyalar joriy etilishi orqali mahsulot tannarxi kamayadi.
3. Brend boshqaruvi va eksport salohiyati oshadi.
4. Tadbirkorlik subyektlari o'rtasida raqobat muhitining sog'lom rivojlanishi ta'minlanadi.

Natijada, O'zbekiston qandolat bozori mintaqaviy miqyosda barqaror raqobatbardosh tarmoq sifatida shakllanadi.

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